

mixture on dilution with water (50 ml) gave 2-methylquinazolin-4-one. The product after purification was found to be identical to that reported in literature (mmp, tlc)¹.

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Chemical Examination of *Cassia javanica* Flowers

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IN an earlier communication¹ isolation and structural studies of flavonoids from the flowers of this plant had been reported.

We report in this communication isolation of three aliphatic alcohols (ceryl alcohol, octacosanol and hentriacontanol), β -sitosterol and a new anthocyanin (peonidin-3-O- α -L (-) rhamnopyranoside) from the flowers of *Cassia javanica* Linn.

Alcoholic extract of the flowers of *Cassia javanica* was hydrolysed with aqueous sodium hydroxide and the unsaponifiable material extracted with benzene and chromatographed over alumina column and eluted with different solvent mixtures according to their polarity. Petroleum ether : benzene (4 : 1) fraction yielded β -sitosterol, petroleum ether : benzene (1 : 1) fraction yielded ceryl alcohol, benzene (100%) yielded octacosanol and benzene : ethyl acetate (9 : 1) fraction yielded hentriacontanol.

These compounds were identified by mp, mmp, derivatisation and I.R., nmr spectra and mass fragmentation pattern.

The fresh flowers of *Cassia javanica* were extracted with ethanolic hydrochloric acid at room temperature. The extract was concentrated at reduced pressure and kept at room temperature and the residue thus obtained was crystallised from amyl alcohol hydrochloric acid mixture. It gave positive Molisch test and other reactions characteristic of anthocyanins. On hydrolysis with 20% hydrochloric acid it gave rhamnose (PC, Osazone) and an aglycone, anthocyanidin which gave specific colour reactions of peonidin derivatives and had λ_{\max} at 542 nm in ethanolic hydrochloric acid solution.

On permanganate oxidation the anthocyanidin gave vanillic acid as one of the oxidation products, which fixed the methoxyl group at position-3' and a hydroxyl group at position-4' in ring B. On alkali degradation the aglycone gave phloroglucinol and vanillic acid. Thus there are hydroxyl groups at position-5, 7 and 4' and a methoxyl group at position-3'. Thus the aglycone is peonidin. Finally, the anthocyanidin was confirmed as peonidin by co-chromatography on paper using Forestal solvent with an authentic sample of peonidin isolated from fresh *Viola tricolor* flowers.

The anthocyanin and anthocyanidin had λ_{\max} at 532 nm and 542 nm respectively in ethanolic hydrochloric acid solution. A hypsochromic shift of 10 nm in the glycoside indicated the attachment of rhamnose in position-3 of peonidin². That rhamnose in the glycoside is in the pyranose form has been proved by periodate oxidation when it consumed 2 moles of periodate per mole of the glycoside and produced 1 mole of formic acid. The glycoside hydrolysed by takadiastase thereby showing the presence of α -linkage. On the basis of these results the glycoside was identified as peonidin-3-O- α -L(-)rhamnopyranoside.

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